

Conference Abstract

Ex-situ conservation of weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) and crucian carp (*Carassius carassius*) in rice fields in Hungary

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Abstract

The practice of rice–fish production dates back to the 15th–12th centuries BC in ancient China (Halwart and Gupta 2004). This symbiotic farming method offers numerous benefits for both rice cultivation and fish rearing. Fish thrive in a protected environment without the need for additional feed, while simultaneously contributing to the control of aquatic insect pests, soil aeration, and plant fertilisation. In Hungary, rice was cultivated on a scale of approximately 50,000–60,000 hectares prior to the 1960s, and carp production in rice fields was developed but declined with the onset of agricultural intensification. The subsequent use of insecticides temporarily halted this organic approach. However, in recent decades, increasing interest in organic rice production has led to a renewed focus on rice–fish systems and related research (Simon-Kiss 2001).

In 2010 and 2012, experiments were conducted in Szarvas, Hungary, in which weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) and crucian carp (*Carassius carassius*) fingerlings were stocked in rice paddies for a two-month rearing period from July to September. The objectives of the study were to assess the growth and survival of these species and to

evaluate the technology for future research and development. Following an unsuccessful preliminary trial with weatherfish in 2010, the experiment was repeated in 2012. Two paddy fields were stocked with fingerlings as follows:

1. field "Monoculture": 250 crucian carp (total length [TL]: 13 ± 1.6 mm)
2. field "Biculture": 250 crucian carp (TL: 13 ± 1.6 mm) and 400 weatherfish (TL: 15 ± 2.6 mm).

The fish adapted well to the agricultural environment and exhibited good growth under extensive rice-fish rearing conditions. Final body weights of weatherfish juveniles ranged from 4.1 to 18.9 g, while crucian carp reached 1.9–18.5 g. Survival rates varied between species, with weatherfish showing a survival rate of 10.5% and crucian carp survival ranging from 36.0% to 40.8%. No statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed in final body weight or survival rates of crucian carp between the monoculture and biculture in rice fields. However, Fulton's condition factor was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in the monoculture system, indicating a slight negative effect on crucian carp growth performance when reared in biculture with weatherfish (Table 1).

Table 1.

Measured and estimated growth parameters in "Monoculture" and "Biculture" rice fields (2012). Values are presented as mean \pm SD where applicable. Kruskal–Wallis test, $p < 0.05$ (SPSS 29.0.10). Different letters indicate significant differences between groups.

Rice field	1. „Monoculture”	2. „Biculture”	
Fish species	<i>Carassius carassius</i>	<i>Carassius carassius</i>	<i>Misgurnus fossilis</i>
Weight (g)	8.1 \pm 2.5 ^{ab}	7.7 \pm 3.0 ^a	10.0 \pm 4.6 ^b
Min.	2.4	1.9	4.1
Max.	18.5	15.3	18.9
Total Length (cm)	6.5 \pm 0.7 ^a	7.3 \pm 0.7 ^b	12.8 \pm 3.2 ^c
Min.	5	5.1	6.1
Max.	9	8.7	19.5
Fulton's condition factor	2.9 \pm 0.4 ^a	1.9 \pm 0.6 ^b	0.5 \pm 0.3 ^c
Min.	1.91	1.32	0.26
Max.	4.17	4.68	1.81
Survival %	40.8 ^a	36 ^a	10.5 ^b

These preliminary observations suggest that rice fields may serve as effective sites for the ex-situ conservation of weatherfish and crucian carp. During the 45-day experimental period, both species exhibited strong performance and high growth potential. Further research is required to optimise the technology and improve the survival and harvesting efficiency of weatherfish. Rice fields represent suitable habitats for the extensive rearing of juvenile fish, while the biological control provided by these species can also support organic rice production (Suppl. material 1).

Keywords

crucian carp, European weatherfish, ex-situ conservation, rice field

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Ex-situ conservation of weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) and crucian carp (*Carassius carassius*) in rice fields in Hungary [doi](#)

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